

TEACHING COMPETENCY OF SECONDARY GRADE TEACHERS BASED ON CERTAIN SELECTED VARIABLES

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Abstract:

In this study, an attempt has been made to study the Teaching competency of secondary grade teachers and its different components, in Trivandrum District of Kerala, India. Also it is intended to study to find out the teaching competency based on the selected subsamples of the study. The Teaching Competency Scale for English Language Teacher (TCSELT) constructed and standardized by Mahalakshmi N (2014) was used to collect the data from the sample of 500 secondary grade teachers, working in Trivandrum District of Kerala, India. The survey method has been followed and the Cluster sampling technique was used in administration of the research. The result of the analysis reveals that the secondary grade teachers are having average level of teaching competency. Also it was found that Male secondary grade teachers are having high level of teaching competency than their counterparts. Secondary grade teachers working in government schools are having relatively high level of teaching competency than those working in private schools and Secondary grade teachers having above 10 years of experience are having relatively high level of teaching competency than other groups.

Key Words: Teaching Competency, , English Teachers, Secondary Grade Teachers, Gender, Type of School & Years of Experience

Introduction:

The term teaching competency has been defined by various authors includes more than mere teacher effects or pupil outcomes. According to some authors it includes knowledge, attitude, skill and other teacher characteristics (Haskew, 1956; Wilson, 1973). Rama (1979) defines teaching competency as "the ability of a teacher manifested through a set of overt teacher classroom behaviours which is a resultant of the interaction between the presage and the product variables of teaching within a social setting".

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the level of teaching competency of secondary grade teachers
- To study the significant difference if any, in teaching competency of secondary grade teachers based on a). Gender b). Type of school and c). Years of experience
- To study the components of teaching competency of secondary grade teachers

Hypotheses of the Study:

- The level of teaching competency of secondary grade teachers is low.
- To study the level of teaching competency of secondary grade teachers based on a). Gender b). Type of school and c). Years of experience is low

Method of Study:

The normative survey method was adopted in this study. The Teaching Competency Scale for English Language Teacher (TCSELT) constructed and standardized by Mahalakshmi N (2014) was used to collect the data from the sample of 500 secondary grade teachers, working in Trivandrum District of Kerala, India. Cluster sampling technique was used in administration of the research tools. Only secondary grade English teachers were included as the sample of this study. Gender, type of school and years of experience were considered as the subsamples of the study. The data collected has been subjected to descriptive analysis.

Analysis of Data and Interpretation:

Descriptive analysis was carried out to analyze the teaching competency scores for the entire and subsamples of the study. The result of the analysis is given in Table-1.

Descriptive Analysis for Teaching Competency Scores

One of the important objectives of the present study is to find out teaching competency levels of secondary grade teachers. For this purpose the traditional method of $M \pm \sigma$ was followed by the investigator.

The mean and standard deviation for the Teaching competency for secondary grade teachers were computed for entire and sub samples of the study. The computed values were given in table -1

Hypothesis 1:

To study the teaching competency secondary grade teachers

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation for the Teaching competency scores of secondary grade teachers

S.No	Variables		Number	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	Entire Sample		500	223.94	14.989
2	Gender	Male	146	229.55	11.922
		Female	354	221.63	15.52
3	Type of School	Government	231	229.16	10.927
		Private	269	219.46	16.499
4	Years of Experience	Below 5 Years	105	221.66	13.039
		5-10 Years	147	220.92	9.266
		Above 10 Years	248	226.54	17.829

From table 1, the calculated mean and standard deviation for teaching competency scores of the entire sample is found to be 223.94 and 14.98 respectively. One can get a maximum score of 250 for teaching competency scale. The mean score lay in between ($M \pm \sigma$) value i.e., 210 to 239. Hence, the framed hypothesis (1) is rejected and it is concluded that secondary grade teachers are having average level of teaching competency.

From table -1, it is observed that the mean values for different sub samples are ranging from 219.46 to 229.55. The mean scores lay in between ($M \pm \sigma$) value i.e., 210 to 239. Hence, the framed hypothesis (2) is rejected it is concluded that secondary grade teachers are having average level of teaching competency with regard to subsamples namely, (i).Male, (ii).Female, (iii) Government, (iv).Private, (v). Below 5 years, (vi). 5-10 years and (vii). Above 10 years.

From table 1, while comparing the group mean scores, it is inferred and concluded that,

- Male secondary grade teachers are having high level of teaching competency than their counterparts.
- Secondary grade teachers working in government schools are having high level of teaching competency than those working in private schools.
- Secondary grade teachers having above 10 years of experience are having high level of teaching competency than other groups.

Teaching Competency Based on the Components:

In order to study the teaching competency based on its components namely, language proficiency, content knowledge, teaching skills, communicative competence and ICT competence, and the mean scores of the components were calculated and tabulated in table – 2.

Table 2: Comparing Teaching competency mean scores based on the components

S.No	Components of Teaching Competency	Sample (N)	Mean Score	Standard Deviation
1	Language Proficiency	500	45.94	3.865
2	Content Knowledge	500	45.26	4.542
3	Teaching skills	500	46.06	3.881
4	Communicative competence	500	46.15	3.683
5	ICT competence	500	40.53	5.225

From table 2, it is visible that secondary grade teachers are having high level of competency in teaching skills, communicative competence, language proficiency, content knowledge and ICT competence in rank order. While comparing the mean scores, it is concluded that secondary grade teachers are having relatively low level of ICT competence in comparison to the other components of teaching competency namely, (i) teaching skills, (ii) communicative competence (iii) language proficiency and (iv) content knowledge.

Figure 1: Line graph showing the difference in mean scores of teaching competency based on its components

The graphical representation of the variation in mean scores of teaching competency based on its components is given in Figure 1.

Major Findings of the Study:

- Secondary grade teachers are having average level of teaching competency.
- Male secondary grade teachers are having relatively high level of teaching competency than their counterparts.
- Secondary grade teachers working in government schools are having relatively high level of teaching competency than those working in private schools.
- Secondary grade teachers with above 10 years of experience are having relatively high level of teaching competency than other groups.
- Secondary grade teachers are having relatively low level of ICT competence in comparison to the other components of teaching competency namely, (i) teaching skills, (ii) communicative competence (iii) language proficiency and (iv) content knowledge.

Discussion and Implications:

In this study, an attempt has been made to study the Teaching competency of secondary grade teachers and its different components, in Trivandrum District of Kerala, India. Also it is intended to study to find out the teaching competency based on the selected subsamples of the study. It was found that secondary grade teachers are having average level of teaching competency. This finding is being supported by Philip simon (2010) and Amaladoss Xavier (2009) and Mahalakshmi N (2014); not supported by Chilambarasan (2011) and Jayakanthan (2003). While comparing the mean scores, it is concluded that secondary grade teachers are having relatively low level of ICT competence in comparison to the other components of teaching competency namely, (i) teaching skills, (ii) communicative competence (iii) language proficiency and (iv) content knowledge. This finding implies that secondary grade teachers are low ICT competence, so that they can be given orientation and workshops to improve their ICT skills.

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